

APPENDIX 3 - SDP3: DETAILED EXECUTION AND ANALYSIS

This Appendix presents a detailed discussion about all the PROV-SwProcess Competency Questions, using data from SDP3 and including the manager's opinion on each of them (the same procedure reported for SDP1 was followed, changing only the scenario and the subject).

Goal 1: Process structure identification during execution and possibilities for process redesign

– **CQ1** *What are the process activities, artifacts, resources, procedures, stakeholders, and the relations among them during the process execution?*

Considering the analysis possibility presented by CQ1 (*It is possible to identify all the process elements that participated in the process execution and the relation among them*) and its respective decision-making possibility (*After identifying the process elements and the relation between them it is possible to find gaps – elements without association or inadequate relation established*), when using iSPuP tool support and the generated macro visualization about SDP3 (shown on Figure 7.15), a stakeholder was identified as 'NULL' (an orange pentagon in the lower center of the figure), associated with some tasks and artifacts. When hovering the mouse over it, it was verified that this stakeholder acted as a developer, modifying versions 0, 3 and 5 of the analyzed project (Figure I.1). Based on this, we consider this fact as a gap possibility: some unidentified person performed these tasks and changed project artifacts and this information was not properly stored. If this is recurring, this can lead to problems in the project development, such as tracking people who have modified a particular artifact or performed some activity.

Figure I.1: SDP3 – Null Stakeholder.

When this analysis was presented to the manager, the following answers were obtained:

- a) This analysis is *correct*.
- b) This analysis *can* assist in the proposed decision-making.
- c) He *cannot* answer CQ1 using his current process management tool.
- d) Answering CQ1 is *extremely relevant* to support in analysis and decision-making processes.

– **CQ2** Which procedures are used by the process during its execution?

Using SDP3 provided data, CQ3 was not possible to be answered since no procedure was informed in the process execution data. However, as it was done with SDP1, we showed to the process manager an analysis possibility in CQ2 using the toy example, and the following answers were obtained from him (we do not make the question to check if the analysis is correct, considering he does not know in details the process used in the toy - only a quick explanation of it was provided at the beginning of the interview):

- a) -
- b) This analysis *can* assist in the proposed decision-making.
- c) He *cannot* answer CQ2 using his current process management tool.
- d) Answering CQ2 is *very relevant* to support in analysis and decision-making processes.

– **CQ3:** Which activities had a high complexity (considering the number of associated stakeholders, artifacts, procedures and / or resources)?

In order to answer CQ3, the activity's degree was used. Figures I.2 and I.3 are generated by the visualization tool to support CQ3. The tabular view was used, and we filter all the activities. After that, we ordered the obtained results by its degree - firstly descending (Fig. I.2) and, after that, ascending (Fig. I.3). According to what is shown, it is possible to see a great discrepancy between the degree of *Issue Resolution* activities and the other two (*Issue Registration* and *Issue Attribution*).

id	Name	Type	Degree
65	Issue_Resolution_2556	Activity	17
72	Issue_Resolution_2674	Activity	16
111	Issue_Resolution_2522	Activity	16
151	Issue_Resolution_2853	Activity	16
107	Issue_Resolution_2526	Activity	13
87	Issue_Resolution_2543	Activity	11
105	Issue_Resolution_2525	Activity	9
264	Issue_Resolution_3083	Activity	8
46	Issue_Resolution_2565	Activity	6
161	Issue_Resolution_2727	Activity	6

Figure I.2: SDP3 – Activities Degree – Part 1.

id	Name	Type	Degree
1	Issue_Registration_2718	Activity	1
5	Issue_Attribution_3631	Activity	1
6	Issue_Attribution_3632	Activity	1
8	Issue_Attribution_2543	Activity	1
12	Issue_Attribution_2536	Activity	1
13	Issue_Attribution_3624	Activity	1
14	Issue_Registration_2722	Activity	1
15	Issue_Registration_2724	Activity	1
17	Issue_Registration_2727	Activity	1
19	Issue_Attribution_3640	Activity	1

Figure I.3: SDP3 – Activities Degree – Part 2.

When this analysis was presented to the manager, the following answers were obtained:

- a) This analysis is *partially correct*. He justified his answer saying that only the degree of the activity cannot be determinant to evaluate its complexity. This may be an ‘indicator’ of that, but, in order to assert this, it would require a more in-depth analysis considering the activity to be developed.
- b) This analysis *can* assist in the proposed decision-making.
- c) He *cannot* answer CQ3 using his current process management tool.
- d) Answering CQ3 is *very relevant* to support in analysis and decision-making processes.

– **CQ4:** *Which activities had a high dependency (on other activities)?*

Activities dependency on other activities is provided by PROV-SwProcess Model using the relation *WasInformedBy* (implying that there has been the exchange of some artifact by two activities, one activity using (or changing) some artifact generated by the other activity) and is useful only when just one instance is analyzed. When checking SDP3 instances separately, no dependency between activities was found, because none of the artifacts generated during the 133 analyzed instances was used or

modified by another activity in the same instance. We discussed this fact with the manager, and the following points should be considered:

- a) This analysis is *correct*.
- b) This analysis *can* assist in the proposed decision-making.
- c) He *cannot* answer CQ4 using his current process management tool.
- d) Answering CQ4 is *extremely relevant* to support in analysis and decision-making processes.

Goal 2: Understanding stakeholder’s involvement in process execution

– **CQ5:** *What is the activities distribution among stakeholders?*

Figure I.4 is generated by the visualization tool to support in answering CQ5.

id	Name	Type	Degree	Created Artifacts	Modified Artifacts	Associated Activities
42	user_29	Person_Stakeholder	391	18	16	368
43	user_26	Person_Stakeholder	19	1	1	14
357	user_41	Person_Stakeholder	24	1	8	14
248	NULL	Person_Stakeholder	7	0	3	3

Figure I.4: SDP3 - Stakeholders X Activities – Tabular View.

Considering the *Person* stakeholders, while *user_26* and *user_41* performed the same number of activities, *user_29* executed 354 more activities than them. Through this tabular visualization, a poor activity distribution between these three stakeholders is clearly perceived. The visualization of which these activities are can be obtained using the graph representation (filtering only the stakeholders and the activities).

When this analysis was presented to the manager, the following answers were obtained:

- a) This analysis is *correct*.
- b) This analysis *can partially* assist in the proposed decision-making. Considering the presented decision-making possibility, it should be considered not only the number of associated activities, but also the time of accomplishment of these activities.
- c) He *cannot* answer CQ5 using his current process management tool.
- d) Answering CQ5 is *extremely relevant* to support in analysis and decision-making processes.

– **CQ6:** Which artifacts are known by a stakeholder, considering that in some process execution he/she created or modified such artifact?

Figure I.5 is an example of visualization generated by the tool to support answering CQ6. According to this figure, we can see, for example, that both *user_26* and *user_29* manipulated *Version_1* and *Version_3* and only stakeholder *user_26* manipulated *Version_2*, *Version_15*, *Version_16*, and *Version_21*, for example. Specifically, in the case of SDP3, no data were provided of which project-specific artifacts were created, modified or changed. Only the information of the project versions that were created, altered or used during the activities was provided for this analysis.

Figure I.5: SDP3 – Stakeholders and Associated Artifacts.

When this analysis was presented to the manager, the following answers were obtained:

- This analysis is *correct*.
- This analysis *can partially* assist in the proposed decision-making.
- He *cannot* answer CQ6 using his current process management tool.
- Answering CQ6 is *extremely relevant* to support in analysis and decision-making processes.

– **CQ7:** Which stakeholders are out of the average of created and/or modified artifacts?

In the case of SDP3, the same visualization generated for CQ6 (Figure I.5) can be used for CQ7 and we can easily see that the stakeholder *user_26* stands out from the other stakeholders when the number of manipulated artifacts is analyzed. The exact number of manipulated artifacts can be obtained through the tabular view (Figure I.6). As a decision-making possibility in relation to this fact, it is suggested a better distribution of the activities among the stakeholders because, considering that much more activities were assigned to this user (*user_26*), this made him/her manipulate much more artifacts than the other users.

id	Name	Type	Degree	Created Artifacts	Modified Artifacts
42	user_29	Person_Stakeholder	391	18	16
43	user_26	Person_Stakeholder	19	1	1
357	user_41	Person_Stakeholder	24	1	8
248	NULL	Person_Stakeholder	7	0	3

Figure I.6: SDP2 - Stakeholders X Created and Artifacts – Tabular View.

When this analysis was presented to the manager, the following answers were obtained:

- a) This analysis is *correct*.
- b) This analysis *can* assist in the proposed decision-making.
- c) He *cannot* answer CQ7 using his current process management tool.
- d) Answering CQ7 is *not very relevant* to support in analysis and decision-making processes.

– **CQ8:** What are the relationships among stakeholders?

Using SDP3 provided data, CQ8 was not possible to be answered since no relation among stakeholders' roles was informed in the process execution data and this information was not inferred by PROV-SwProcess. However, we showed to the process manager an analysis possibility in CQ8 using the toy example, and the following answers were obtained from him:

- a) -
- b) This analysis *can* assist in the proposed decision-making.

- c) He *cannot* answer CQ8 using his current process management tool.
- d) Answering CQ8 is *extremely relevant* to support in analysis and decision-making processes.

– **CQ9:** Which roles does each stakeholder assume?

Figure I.7 is generated to support in answering CQ9. Using this figure, we can see that *user_26* and *user_29* performed all the 3 process roles, while *user_41* and the ‘NULL’ user (presented in the CQ1 analysis) acted only as developer. As a decision-making possibility the manager can check if this fact was really planned and, if yes, in a next instantiation of this process, if the process manager needs to allocate a *Programmer*, a *Manager* or a *Developer* in a specific activity, he knows who can perform these roles, based on previous execution data.

Figure I.7: SDP2 - Stakeholders x Roles.

When this analysis was presented to the manager, the following answers were obtained:

- a) This analysis is *correct*.
- b) This analysis *can* assist in the proposed decision-making.
- c) He *cannot* answer CQ9 using his current process management tool.
- d) Answering CQ9 is *very relevant* to support in analysis and decision-making processes.

Goal 3: Tracking derivations and revisions among artifacts or procedures

– **CQ10:** Which artifacts are derivations from others? and

– **CQ11:** Which artifacts or procedures are revisions from others?

Considering SDP3, no derivation between artifacts was inferred. This fact occurs because only the information about created and changed versions was informed, and no information was provided about what versions were used by the activities.

When this analysis was presented to the manager, the following answers were obtained (both for CQ10 and CQ11):

- a) This analysis is *correct*, considering only the analyzed group of data.
- b) This analysis *can* assist in the proposed decision-making.
- c) He *can* answer CQ10 and CQ11 using his current process management tool.
- d) Answering CQ10 and CQ11 is *extremely relevant* to support in analysis and decision-making processes.